

FRAXINUS L. SPECIES IN URBAN GREENING

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Abstract. In recent years, the scale of construction of new cities, residential areas and highways has been increasing in our Republic. In connection with this, it is of great importance to carry out landscaping and improvement works in these territories.

Key words. *Fraxinus excelsior* L, *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* March, *Fraxinus americana* L.

In recent years, the scale of construction of new cities, settlements and roads in our Republic has been increasing. In this regard, landscaping and improvement work in these territories is of great importance. In landscaping, the sharply continental climatic conditions of our Republic, as well as the improvement of newly built cities and our southern hot regions, require sufficient knowledge and skills from specialists in this field. The reason is that the correct selection of tree and shrub species for these areas is based on their bioecological characteristics. It is necessary to take into account soil conditions, increase soil fertility, correctly select and plant trees and shrubs, and correctly use local and organic fertilizers.

Fraxinus excelsior L

Botanical classification: A fast-growing, dark shade ornamental tree, belonging to the Olive family, reaching a height of 30-40 m. The leaves are flat, opposite. It blooms in April-May. The flowers are bisexual and unisexual, and the fruit ripens in September. After ripening, it begins to shed slowly, a part of it is stored on the tree throughout the winter, and all is shed before the leaves are written in spring. Common sycamore is a light-loving plant that lives up to 200-250 years.

Homeland: Europe, Crimea and the Caucasus.

Distribution: This species is widespread and occurs in the Crimea and the Caucasus, in the Carpathian Mountains. There are more than 60 species of this family on earth. There are currently more than 20 introduced species in the Botanical Garden

Recommendations for propagation and planting: *Fraxinus excelsior* is very easy to propagate from seeds. Sowing time: Sow freshly picked seeds in the fall to a depth of 1.5-2 cm. If the seeds are sown in the spring, they are soaked in warm water. After two years, the seedlings are planted in the spring in a nursery in a checkerboard pattern of 80x100 cm. When planted in a row, the distance between the trees is 6 m, and when planted in a group, the distance is 6x6 m. The sun-loving plant is not picky about soil type, it is resistant to drought and extreme weather conditions, gases and diseases. In landscaping, it is used to create protective environments that provide deep shade in urban parks, alleys and recreation areas, mainly along roadsides.

It is recommended for planting in all regions of our republic, except deserts and saline lands. Pennsylvania ash - *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* March

Botanical classification: A decorative tree of the olive family, reaching a height of 30-40 m, providing deep shade. The leaves are elongated, smooth, covered with small teeth on the edges. In Tashkent conditions, it blooms and bears fruit in March-April every year. The fruits ripen in October.

Homeland: North America.

Distribution: Widely distributed in Canada, Ontario, Texas, and European countries. There are more than 60 species in the world. Currently, there are more than 20 species in the Botanical Garden.

Propagation and planting recommendations: *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* is propagated by seed. Sowing time: Freshly picked seeds are sown in the fall at a depth of 1.5-2 cm. If the seeds are sown in the spring, they are soaked in warm water. After two years, the seedlings are planted in the nursery in the spring in a checkerboard pattern of 100x120 cm.

In landscaping, the distance between trees is 8 m when planted in a row, and 8x8 m when planted in a group. The sun-loving plant is not picky about soil type, is resistant to drought and extreme climatic conditions, gases and diseases. In landscaping, it is used to create protective environments that provide deep shade in cities, parks, avenues, recreation areas and along highways.

It is recommended for planting in all regions of our republic, except deserts and highly saline lands.

American ash - *Fraxinus americana* L

Botanical classification: A decorative shade tree belonging to the olive family, reaching a height of 30-40m. Its leaves are elongated, smooth, covered with small teeth on the edges. The trunk is strong, used to make quality furniture. It blooms in April. The fruit ripens in October.

Homeland: North America.

Distribution: Widely distributed in Canada, Ontario, Texas, and Europe. There are more than 60 species worldwide. Currently, there are more than 20 species in the Botanical Garden.

Reproduction and planting recommendations *Fraxinus americana* is propagated by seed. Sowing time Freshly picked seeds are sown in the fall at a depth of 1.5-2 cm. If the seeds are sown in spring, they are soaked in warm water. After two years, the seedlings are planted in a nursery in the spring in a 100x120 cm spacing and in a checkerboard pattern.

In landscaping, the distance between trees is 8 m when planted in a row, and 8x8 m when planted in a group. The sun-loving plant is not picky about soil type, is resistant to drought and extreme climatic conditions, gases and diseases. In landscaping, it is used to create protective environments that provide deep shade in cities, parks, avenues, recreation areas and along highways.

It is recommended to plant in all regions of our republic, except for the desert and strongly saline lands.

Large plantations, built in accordance with the requirements of the environmental conditions of plants and in compliance with the relevant agrotechnical rules, can fully demonstrate their sanitary and hygienic properties. Tree species should be placed taking into account their ecological and biological characteristics: light, soil, moisture requirements, and the degree of mutual compatibility in time and space. The width of the distance between plants and structures should be selected taking into account the growth of tree branches.

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